

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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T1.3_Spain Lab 2nd Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Ferrol, Galicia

EVENT DATE: 12th March 2024 (from 9.30 AM to 2.30 PM)

EVENT TITLE: OFFSHORE WIND IN GALICIA

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

LEAD ORGANISER: Sener

CO-ORGANISERS: -

LANGUAGE: Spanish and Galician

CONCEPT

The Second Co-creation Workshop in Spain had a primary focus on the latest advancements in Floating Offshore Wind Technologies. This event was closely associated with the Horizon Europe project MARINEWIND, which is financially supported by the European Commission. Specifically, the workshop took place at the Industrial Campus of Ferrol, Galicia. This location was chosen due to its significance in the context of floating offshore wind energy in Galicia. The workshop was divided into two main parts. The first part featured 14 speakers distributed across four thematic tables:

Table 1: Regulatory Framework and Context of Marine Wind Energy

Table 2: The Role of Academia, Industry, and Technological Centers

Table 3: Environmental Vision of Marine Wind Energy

Table 4: Impact on Different Sectors

Each table addressed specific aspects related to the implementation and development of marine wind energy in Galicia. Participants had the opportunity to listen to presentations from experts in each field and engage in debates that fostered enriching idea exchange.

The second part of the workshop consisted of a debate where all participants could engage. This segment allowed for deeper conversations about various aspects and divergent perspectives regarding the implementation of offshore wind energy in the Galician region. The diversity of viewpoints on this important matter further enriched the discussions.

OBJECTIVES To discuss barriers and facilitators to offshore wind deployment in Spain, and specifically in Galicia.

TARGET AUDIENCE: The participation included representatives of the 5-Helix stakeholders' groups:

- Industry: FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, fisheries, local traders, etc.
- Civil Society: civil society organisations, renewable organisations, etc.
- Academia: scientific community and public/private research organisations.
- Public Authorities: Galician and local government.
- Green Innovation: ecologists, environmental organisations and green cooperatives.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 38 participants

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

The choice of speakers was made with the intention of ensuring a balanced representation of the 5-helix stakeholders and topics under analysis by Marinewind (policy measures, societal engagement and environmental impact financial solutions, techno-economic implications, and commercialization of FOWT). Furthermore, the speakers' participation was organized into four distinct categories:

2.1 Assessing the current regulatory framework and context of Marine Wind Energy

Victor Ledo, Secretary General of CCOO Industry of Galicia

Victor Ledo emphasizes the importance of utilizing local expertise and resources in the development of offshore wind energy projects. He highlights that the region has already been involved in the creation of foundations for floating wind farms, presenting it as "a golden opportunity to capitalize on this experience." Ledo stresses the necessity for promoters aspiring to install offshore wind farms to **prioritize manufacturing all value-added components, including towers, blades, and turbines, within Galicia**. This approach aims to ensure maximum industrial production and quality employment within the region.

Moreover, Ledo underscores that the commitment to offshore wind energy is crucial for reducing energy prices for both domestic consumers and industrial sectors. He sees it as a step towards reducing the country's heavy reliance on energy imports and positioning Galicia as a global leader in offshore wind technologies. He advocates for offshore wind energy to become a **priority for the industrial diversification** of the country, which currently faces significant challenges due to its energy import dependence.

Additionally, Ledo emphasizes the importance of **education** within the local community to ensure that individuals are equipped with the necessary skills to benefit from job opportunities arising from the offshore wind industry. This includes advocating for university education, training courses, and other forms of education to empower the community to actively participate in and benefit from this industry.

Javier Gómez, Port Authority of Ferrol – San Cibrao

Javier Gómez represents the Port Authority of Ferrol – San Cibrao, showcasing the **experiences** of the Ferrol port in operations related to offshore wind energy. He introduces projects like the Ferrol Fow initiative, set to be unveiled to the industrial and logistics sectors in the coming days. The presence of various stakeholders in these forums, including developers, technologists, logistics professionals, and construction companies, aids in aligning port development with the anticipated strong demand.

Focusing on Ferrol and San Cibrao ports as hubs for offshore wind energy operations, Gómez highlights their capacity to handle tasks such as jacket and spar production, as well as servicing both fixed and floating wind farms. He emphasizes the port's role in providing value-added activities and its vision for the local region. Additionally, Gómez addresses the regulatory framework and mentions the port's

involvement in projects like WindFloat and monopile production, as well as storage of large components and maintenance bases.

In terms of operational aspects, Gómez touches upon various topics such as safety, available surfaces, crane facilities, costs, and maritime climate. Javier Gómez's presentation provides insight into the Port Authority's efforts to position **Ferrol and San Cibrao as key players** in the offshore wind energy sector, demonstrating their capabilities, vision, and commitment to facilitating the growth of this industry within the region.

Raquel Juan, Sener

Raquel Juan, representing Sener, delves into the regulatory framework of offshore wind energy in Spain, outlining the various aspects and developments shaping the industry. She begins by discussing the roadmap for offshore wind and marine energies in Spain, highlighting key areas such as innovation hubs, value chain development, sustainable development, and the state framework for orderly deployment.

She then moves on to discuss recent environmental assessments and strategic planning, including the evaluation of maritime spatial planning and the regulatory framework under *Real Decreto 1028/2007*, which has been in moratorium since 2021. Juan emphasizes the ongoing consultation process for a new royal decree and the impending ministerial orders related to auctions and administrative authorizations.

During her presentation, Juan provides insights into the competitive bidding process, which involves initial ministerial orders, a dialogue phase, and eventual resolution, with criteria including socioeconomic factors. She highlights the importance of considering various project types, including pre-commercial parks, innovative marine renewable installations, and coordination guarantees. Further, Juan discusses the applicable regulations governing renewable energy production, access, connection, economic regimes, and coastal regulations, emphasizing the need for a clear regulatory framework to address industry uncertainties.

In conclusion, Juan underscores **the need for a comprehensive regulatory framework and a medium-term auction calendar to provide clarity and stability for stakeholders** in the offshore wind energy sector in Spain. She acknowledges the openness of the current royal decree consultation process, stressing the importance of addressing industry concerns and providing a clear roadmap for future developments.

2.2 Delving into the role of Academia, Industry, and Technological Centres

Lucía Fraga, Head of the Training Department at CETMAR

Lucía Fraga introduces the FLORES project, part of the Offshore Renewable Energies Partnership in the Pact for Skills co-funded by the European Union. She outlines the stakeholders involved in the ORESkills consortia, including policymakers, standardization bodies, social partners, professional bodies,

education and training providers, and employers, all working together to address skill needs in the offshore renewable energy (ORE) sector.

The main outcomes of the project focus on developing a **blueprint for shipbuilding and offshore renewables**, supporting the internal organization of the ORE Skills partnership and fostering innovative solutions. An observatory is established to gather skills intelligence for the ORE sector, analysing present skill needs, mapping training offerings, and forecasting future trends.

Expected results include stimulating dedicated training offers for the ORE sector, promoting innovative approaches in lifelong learning, creating a repository of training materials, and providing assistance through a helpdesk for lifelong learning and vocational education and training standards. Additionally, the project aims to **enhance career and job opportunities** in the ORE sector by providing multilingual educational materials and updating the ESCO Occupational Profiles. Fraga emphasizes the continued efforts of the ORESkills partnership to promote skilling processes in the ORE sector, fostering collaboration among its members, and expanding participation. The partnership integrates with other consortia, such as the Shorewinner project, to further enhance its impact and reach in the ORE sector.

Laura Castro, Associate Professor at University. Escola Politécnica de Enxeñaría de Ferrol, CITENI, Industrial Campus of Ferrol, University of A Coruña

Laura emphasized the significance of research and introduced CITENI, a research centre specializing in naval and industrial technologies. Laura highlighted their work in assessing the social cost of energy and their involvement in areas like floating offshore wind, wave energy, hybrid systems, and marine solar energy. Tools such as W2EC (Wind & Wave Energy Calculator) and SEARENEW (Sea Energy Farm Economic Calculator) were presented as part of their research efforts.

Regarding education, Laura announced that the Ferrol School of Engineering, located within the University of A Coruña's Industrial Campus, will launch a **university program focusing on marine wind energy**. Given its strategic importance to the Galician autonomous community, particularly due to its connections with shipyards and the naval industry, she introduced the master in ongoing training in floating marine wind energy for the academic year 2024/2025. The main objective is to serve as a foundation for **training** marine wind energy companies and their affiliates, both locally and nationally. Laura aims to educate professionals from various fields, including those from regional engineering schools. The goal is **to position Ferrol as a leader in floating marine wind energy**, not only in terms of construction with its shipyards but also in education with this master's program.

Santiago Rodríguez, Director of Energy at the Galician Institute of Technology (ITG)

During his presentation at the conference, Rodríguez articulated the **pressing challenges confronting offshore wind energy** with precision and urgency. He began by outlining the multifaceted nature of these challenges, emphasizing the critical need to quantify and manage impacts across various dimensions—social, environmental, economic, and industrial. Rodríguez stressed the imperative of **engaging stakeholders** and developing robust **tools for comprehensive impact assessment and management**.

Moving on, Rodríguez underscored the daunting task of integrating substantial volumes of variable renewable energy into specific nodes of terrestrial grids with unwavering quality and reliability. He elucidated the complexities inherent in this endeavour and underscored its paramount importance for optimizing the efficiency and efficacy of offshore wind energy initiatives within broader energy systems. Further, Rodríguez delved into the hurdles associated with the operation and maintenance (O&M) of offshore wind infrastructure. With examples such as annual cable failures and projected losses for 2030, he painted a picture of the challenges ahead. Importantly, Charlón emphasized the **need of minimizing human intervention and vessel utilization to curtail costs and mitigate downtime**—a point he emphasized with emphasis.

Finally, Rodríguez advocated for a holistic approach to tackling these challenges, emphasizing the need for tailored developments in independent monitoring and advanced digitalization. He underscored the importance of pioneering research and development efforts in cutting-edge technologies like USV (Unmanned Surface Vehicle), artificial intelligence, computer vision, robotics, and prescriptive AI-based O&M strategies for electrical infrastructure. Through his impassioned delivery, Rodríguez left a **call to action, urging collective effort and innovation to surmount the obstacles and secure the sustainable future of offshore wind energy.**

María Campos, from the Association of Metal Industries and Associated Technologies of Galicia (ASIME)

María Campos, representing ASIME, provided insights into offshore wind projects, illustrating their substantial impact on the region. She highlighted that these projects generate 57,000 jobs, contribute to 20% of Galicia's GDP, and boast over 600 associated companies. Campos underscored the significant opportunities these projects offer for **economic growth and development.**

Moreover, Campos discussed initiatives such as Erasmus+ FLORES, aimed at enhancing training within the marine renewable energy sector. She also addressed the Bay H2 Offshore project, which focuses on developing and constructing a pilot plant to produce green ammonia synthesized from green hydrogen generated by marine renewable energies. She emphasized the synergy between industries fostered by such projects. Additionally, Campos elaborated on the Industrial Support Plan and Value Chain Enhancement linked to offshore wind energy in the Galicia-Northern Portugal Euroregion. This plan aims to attract new actors, provide specialized training, and promote offshore wind energy in alignment with the European Green Deal.

Finally, key activities were outlined, such as the development of a cross-border roadmap, industry support, awareness campaigns and value chain design. In her presentation, Campos highlighted the **importance of collaboration, innovation and strategic planning** to drive the offshore wind energy sector in the region.

2.3 Environmental Vision of Marine Wind Energy

Miguel Gil, Institute of Marine Research (CSIC)

Miquel Gil, representing the Institute of Marine Research, provides an oceanographic perspective on offshore wind energy. His presentation, titled "Oceanographic Vision of Offshore Wind Energy: Energy Reservoirs," delves into the interaction between wind energy and marine environments.

Gil begins by emphasizing that wind primarily drives ocean currents, significantly influencing energy distribution. He highlights coastal upwellings along our shores, where surface water movements enhance primary production. He discusses the changes in wind velocity profiles caused by wind turbines, noting how they extract energy from the wind and generate turbulence, affecting surface water temperature and humidity.

The presentation underscores the **importance of understanding the spatial and temporal distribution of wind energy over the sea**, as wind farms can impact wind intensity and turbulence, with wake effects extending up to 40-50 km. These changes in wind patterns can alter surface currents, affecting various oceanographic processes, including biological, sedimentary, and biogeochemical dynamics. He acknowledges the uncertainties surrounding the impacts of offshore wind energy on marine ecosystems but emphasizes the necessity of reducing these uncertainties through observation and modelling. He stresses the importance of interdisciplinary and ecosystem-based approaches in managing natural resources effectively.

In conclusion, Gil highlights **the need for further research to mitigate uncertainties and properly assess the potential negative and positive impacts** of offshore wind energy on marine ecosystems. He advocates for enhanced observation and modelling efforts to better understand and manage the complex interactions between offshore wind energy and oceanographic processes.

Guillermo Bouza, representing the marine consultancy Tecnoambiente

Guillermo Bouza briefly outlines the concept of environmental assessment, encompassing both strategic environmental assessment and impact assessment. He proceeds to discuss the process of environmental impact assessment, focusing on the **identification of potential impacts and key environmental factors**. He highlights major environmental impacts, including those on avifauna, marine mammals, landscape, fishing activity, habitat alteration, and hydrodynamic regimes. Additionally, he explores **opportunities associated** with offshore wind energy, such as increased bird foraging areas, species refuge, enhanced reproductive success, nutrient enrichment, habitat creation, and biodiversity enhancement. He emphasizes the importance of considering designated natural spaces, such as the ZEPA (Special Protection Areas for Birds), particularly the Galician-Cantabrian migratory corridor, in project planning.

Bouza underscores the **significance of mitigating impacts** on avifauna, including collision risks, displacement, barrier effects, and alterations to food resources. He outlines methodologies for large-scale studies, including the identification of important bird and marine mammal areas, inventory of associated communities, and estimation of abundance and density through fieldwork. Furthermore, Bouza discusses the importance of minimizing impacts on marine habitats, including rocky substrates

and sedimentary bottoms, while also addressing fishing interactions, landscape considerations, and public engagement.

In conclusion, Bouza presents **key recommendations** for thorough marine spatial and temporal analysis, exclusion criteria for protected areas, adherence to ZEPAs regulations, utilization of best-available techniques for offshore studies, standardized methodologies for avifauna census, and stakeholder engagement. He emphasizes the importance of ongoing **monitoring and evaluation** to ensure environmental sustainability in offshore wind energy projects.

Bruno Díaz, from the Bottlenose Dolphin Research Institute

Bruno Díaz, addresses the topic of "Cetaceans and Offshore Wind Farms: Cetaceans as Indicators of Environmental Health." Díaz emphasizes the importance of cetaceans as indicators of environmental well-being and advocates for their consideration in offshore wind farm planning and decision-making processes. He underscores the need to identify vulnerable areas for cetacean species and evaluate potential negative ecological impacts before making decisions. Díaz stresses the importance of assessing cumulative environmental impacts and adhering to the precautionary principle in development. He emphasizes the significance of **incorporating impact data and ongoing monitoring into decision-making processes**.

Díaz highlights common impacts on cetaceans resulting from the installation and operation of offshore wind farms, including physical effects, stress, physiological changes, auditory impairment, and behavioural alterations. He points out the lack of scientific studies due to insufficient information, emphasizing the need for species inventories, spatial and temporal distribution analyses, abundance and density assessments, and conservation status evaluations for cetacean species.

Furthermore, Díaz advocates for an ecosystem-based approach to minimize vulnerability and address uncertainties surrounding offshore wind farm impacts on cetaceans. He urges caution against misinformation and emphasizes the importance of avoiding sensationalized claims. Díaz concludes by urging stakeholders to **prioritize scientific research and evidence-based decision-making** to ensure the protection of cetaceans and their habitats in the development of offshore wind energy projects.

2.4 Analysing the effects on diverse sectors influenced by this technology

Fabian Ben, Project Director at the National Federation of Fishermen's Guilds

Fabian Ben, representing the National Federation of Fishermen's Guilds, expressed the organization's stance on offshore wind energy development and its implications for the fishing sector. He emphasized that while the Fishermen's Guilds **do not oppose renewable energies**, they advocate for a fair ecological transition for the fishing industry. Conde highlighted concerns regarding the risks posed to fishing-related jobs and the livelihoods of coastal communities by the development of offshore wind energy projects.

Conde raised the issue of **food sovereignty**, noting that a significant portion of Spain's fish consumption is imported. He cautioned that reducing the fishing fleet and activity could jeopardize Spain's food sovereignty. Furthermore, Conde discussed the dual nature of the Blue Economy, acknowledging both its potential and threats to the fishing sector. **He criticized governments' prioritization of activities like offshore wind energy overfishing**, emphasizing the potential consequences of such decisions.

Highlighting the economic significance of small-scale fishing fleets, Conde provided statistics on the number of boats and jobs generated in Spain. He emphasized the substantial value-added by these fleets, both economically and culturally, underscoring the importance of recognizing the full economic value generated by the fishing sector. Conde concluded by stressing the importance of conducting thorough environmental impact assessments before implementing offshore wind projects. **He warned against proceeding without accurate data on the potential impacts on fishing activity and marine biodiversity**, emphasizing the irreversible consequences such actions could entail.

Oriol Sarmiento, Manager of the Renewable Energy Cluster of Galicia (CLUERGAL)

Oriol Sarmiento, focused his presentation on offshore wind energy and its value chain, in the context of Spain. He highlighted Spain's urgent **need for skilled professionals** in this sector, second only to Germany. Notably, Sarmiento drew attention to the **lessons learned from onshore wind energy development in Galicia**, emphasizing the importance of **avoiding past mistakes** in the offshore sector.

Discussing the development of the value chain, Sarmiento stressed the necessity of various components, including vessels, shipyards, ports, equipment, logistics, engineering, installation, and operations and maintenance. He underscored the significant economic and employment effects associated with each stage of the value chain. Sarmiento concluded by advocating for a strong commitment to offshore wind energy, emphasizing the need for maximum environmental respect, social agreements, resolution of conflicts with fishermen, establishment of industry, value chain establishment, innovation, and collaboration with technological centres and engineering firms. Through his presentation, Sarmiento outlined a **comprehensive strategy for advancing the offshore wind energy sector while ensuring sustainability, social cohesion, and economic growth**.

Helena Brage, from Parque Nordés

Helena Brage's presentation focused on the socio-economic impact of floating offshore wind energy, particularly within the context of a future offshore park, Parque Nordés, in the waters of Galicia. She provided details about the proposed offshore farm located in the POEM NOR-2 area, comprising 35 turbines with a total capacity of 525 MW. The park will be situated more than 31 km from the coast, at depths ranging from 200 to 300 meters. She discussed the competitive bidding process for offshore wind projects in Spain, outlining the requirements and criteria that projects must meet to participate in the process. These include aspects related to project design, environmental impact, socio-economic impact, decommissioning, and contribution to electricity supply quality and safety.

Brage stressed the importance of high-quality preliminary studies for the maturity of the project, ensuring its technical, environmental, social, and economic viability. The objective is to guarantee successful and sustainable development, minimizing uncertainties and risks associated with project implementation. To achieve this, the speaker recommended **comprehensive project design, including site characterization through meteorological measurements, environmental impact assessments, and socio-economic impact studies**. Additionally, she highlighted the importance of **involving local and regional investors** in project financing and providing studies on the **coexistence** of offshore wind energy with existing activities, such as fishing.

Brage also presented estimations of job creation associated with the Parque Nordés project, indicating significant **employment opportunities** during construction, decommissioning, and operation and maintenance phases. These include 6,000 jobs during construction and decommissioning, with 2,000 directly impacting Galicia, and 100 annual jobs during operation and maintenance. Through these estimations, she emphasized the potential socio-economic benefits that offshore wind projects can bring to the region.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

Following the presentations, the stage was set for the final debate. The moderator took charge, facilitating questions and ensuring all participants had the opportunity to express their viewpoints. The Mentimeter tool was used in the first instance to open up questions that could then be debated and explored further.

The debate on offshore wind energy in Ferrol touched upon several critical points. It began with a clear assessment of the public administration's role, highlighting a perceived **lack of dialogue promotion**. Participants expressed frustration over the government's insufficient support for fostering social acceptance, indicating that dialogue initiation comes only after the competition launch, which fails to facilitate social acceptance and common ground. Moreover, concerns were raised regarding the **absence of adequate space and port infrastructure** for such deployments, compounded by **exorbitant costs and infrastructure limitations**. Participants also lamented the apparent **impossibility of meeting the 2030 requirements** outlined in the Roadmap for Offshore Wind and Marine Energies and the updated Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan for 2023-2030. With numerous barriers and pervasive uncertainty, it appears unlikely that these objectives will be met—a bitter conclusion further compounded by the absence of governmental representation.

One significant area of discussion centred on the **impact** of offshore wind energy **on the fishing sector**. Participants raised questions regarding pilot tests and voiced apprehension about the potential risk to employment due to insufficient data. They emphasized the importance of fostering **equal conditions for coexistence** between the fishing and renewable energy sectors, particularly considering anticipated growth in the blue economy. Criticism was directed towards perceived industrial secrecy within the fishing sector, which hindered the dissemination of crucial information related to fishing grounds location. Both regional and central administrations were cited as not adequately facilitating dialogue among stakeholders. The need to defend the fishing sector while promoting positive intersectoral relations and developing new models integrating the value chain was underscored. Furthermore, the debate touched upon sustainability concerns within the fishing industry, with participants discussing the sustainability of trawling practices. While some participants contended that regulated trawling, in accordance with Spanish law, is sustainable, others emphasized the importance of not sourcing fish from unregulated third countries. There was consensus on the need to avoid confrontation and instead focus on finding mutually beneficial solutions for coexistence between fishing and offshore wind energy sectors. Additionally, **participants stressed the responsibility of governments in managing discussions between promoters and fishermen**, advocating for proactive governmental involvement in conflict resolution and stakeholder engagement processes.

Another topic addressed the availability of trained professionals to meet the demands of the emerging offshore wind energy sector. Participants highlighted **the need for increased training and educational programs**, including dual training cycles, to cultivate a skilled workforce capable of supporting the industry. They noted the existing shortage of professionals and emphasized the necessity of initiatives

to address this gap. However, it was emphasized that this should not be seen as a downside, but as an **opportunity to grow** as a region in the sector, promoting education and professionals in this area.

The discussion also addressed onshore wind energy in Galicia, highlighting past shortcomings and urging **caution to avoid repeating mistakes** in offshore wind deployment. There were concerns raised about the approval process for onshore wind farms, with environmental reports not being made public. Legal disputes over project approvals have led to significant investment risks. Also, the judicial suspension of 13 new projects underscores the prevailing uncertainty surrounding wind energy development in the region.

Within the context of avoiding repetition of errors, discussions also touched on best practices at a national level. Participants questioned whether there were any clear benchmarks, with references made to the offshore wind park in Portugal and the need to differentiate between recreational fishing and commercial fishing practices. Criteria for managing these fishing methods were discussed, with some asserting that clear benchmarks exist, particularly in Northern Europe. However, uncertainties remain regarding technological differences and challenges with public administrations, leading to concerns about misinformation stemming from auctions and hindering the ability to implement best practices. Examples from countries like Scotland were cited, emphasizing the economic benefits of utilizing local labour and resources. Aligned with the Scottish best practices fostering the local content, the importance of local workforce involvement, including training programs for dockworkers and cargo handling, was underscored, though challenges in providing accreditation for such training were acknowledged.

Furthermore, a comparison between Galicia and Catalonia highlighted disparities in the acceptance of wind energy. While both regions are heavily impacted by the wind industry, Galicia boasts a significant industrial base and has identified clear educational and resource needs. In contrast, Catalonia's opposition to wind energy is more rooted in tourism and cultural heritage concerns, reflecting a more sentimental perspective. These **differences underscore the importance of tailored approaches to wind energy development based on regional contexts and needs.**

The session concluded on an encouraging tone, as participants highlighted the emergence of constructive dialogue between traditionally disconnected stakeholders. Despite the absence of national government representation, attendees expressed their commitment to further collaboration and dialogue at future meetings. It was clear that the conversation during the session would pave the way for improved communication and coordination, fostering a more inclusive approach to offshore wind farm decision-making. Going forward, there is a shared determination to address critical issues and concerns with the involvement of all stakeholders, recognizing the importance of effective governance and stakeholder engagement to ensure the success of such projects.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

To conclude the event, the Mentimeter tool was used to record the baseline questions from all Marine Wind workshops at the various locations.

1. Which of the following categories represents you?

The survey results indicate a diverse distribution among participants. 48% of respondents are from the industry, followed by 16% from universities, and 8% from research entities, institutions, and associations respectively. The remaining 8% identified themselves as "others." It's regrettable that several persons chose not to respond. If everyone had participated, the results would have shown a greater representation from academia, with significant responses also from civil society, green innovation, and industry sectors.

Figure 1 MENTIMETER. Question 1

2. What are the most important enablers for investing in floating offshore wind?

The results for this question indicate a clear preference for a well-defined regulatory framework. These responses are consistent with the conclusions that were addressed in the debate. Specifically, 83% of respondents chose a clear regulatory framework as the most important enabling factor. In addition, 13% of respondents chose the potential for local supply chain development, while 4% identified a large market share and demand. Notably, none of the respondents selected national network stability, presence of incentives or technological maturity as important factors.

Figure 2 MENTIMETER. Question 2

3. In your opinion, where is the most significant risk in the supply chain?

The survey results indicate a variety of perspectives regarding the most significant risk in the supply chain. Out of the respondents, 35% identified infrastructure development as the primary concern, highlighting potential challenges in building necessary infrastructure for floating offshore wind projects. Only 10% of respondents expressed concerns about the availability of specialized vessels for turbine installation. In contrast, 55% of respondents cited the capacity of the local supply chain as the most significant risk, emphasizing the importance of developing and strengthening local supply chains to support the growth of the floating offshore wind industry.

Figure 3 MENTIMETER. Question 3

4. How can the industry better engage with local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of floating offshore wind projects?

In response to the question regarding how the industry can better engage with local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of floating offshore wind projects, participants prioritized actions as follows: Proposing biodiversity recovery plans, highlighting environmental benefits, and implementing safety measures emerged as the most relevant action, indicating a strong emphasis on ecological preservation and community safety. Promoting inclusive decision-making processes, such as municipal meetings and public consultations, ranked second in importance, emphasizing the significance of involving local stakeholders in project planning and decision-making. Sharing environmental and socioeconomic studies ranked third. Implementing educational and community outreach programs, such as workshops and conferences on floating offshore wind technology and its benefits, ranked fourth. Establishing partnerships with local and public organizations ranked fifth. Updating the local community on pilot project outcomes, including platform and prototype developments, ranked sixth. And lastly, informing the local community about the financial benefits of floating offshore wind projects, such as new job opportunities, ranked lowest in priority, suggesting that while financial benefits are important, other considerations such as environmental protection and community engagement take precedence in addressing stakeholders' concerns.

Figure 4 MENTIMETER. Question 4

5. Which are the main environmental concerns associated with floating offshore wind energy?

In this question, participants could select up to three options if they considered it necessary. The most voted option, with 18 responses, representing approximately 31% of the total, was "Impact on marine ecosystems". This was closely followed, representing approximately 24%, by "Habitat degradation/modification". "Noise, electromagnetic fields, thermal pollution" received 10 votes, constituting approximately 17% of the responses. Seven respondents expressed concern about "Visual

impact of FOWT". Four votes were attributed to both "Collision with structures" and "Hydrodynamic changes". "Sediment resuspension" received only one vote and, , the "Potential spills" option received none.

Figure 6 MENTIMETER. Question 5

6. Which infrastructure challenges need to be addressed to support the growth of the floating offshore wind industry?

Participants were asked to select up to three options regarding the main infrastructure challenges needed to support the growth of the floating offshore wind industry. The results indicate a strong emphasis on technological maturity, with 15 votes (approximately 24%) prioritizing this aspect. Following closely is the improvement of network connectivity and transmission infrastructure, garnering significant attention with 13 votes (about 21%). Other notable concerns include addressing supply chain challenges, receiving 9 votes, while the scalability of current solutions to commercial scale and the standardization of new solutions received 3 and 6 votes, respectively. Interestingly, investments in port infrastructure for testing phase did not receive any votes.

Figure 7 MENTIMETER. Question 6

7. What strategies can be employed to build trust and acceptance among the communities where these technologies are being deployed?

Participants were presented with various strategies and asked to select up to three options aimed at fostering trust and acceptance among communities where offshore wind technologies are being deployed. The results highlight a strong preference for increasing environmental studies, with 13 votes (about 22%) emphasizing this approach. Encouraging and supporting local businesses to provide operation and maintenance solutions received 4 votes. Defining fishing areas/zones garnered significant attention with the 18%, as did promoting public participation, also receiving 11 votes. Applying benefit-sharing mechanisms, such as community investment funds or local job creation initiatives, received the 17% of the votes. Meanwhile, minimizing sea use and coexisting conflicts received 2 votes, and developing parameters to evaluate participation and incorporating them into project assessments received 3 votes.

Figure 8 MENTIMETER. Question 7

8. Which activity is most in conflict with the offshore wind sector?

The majority of respondents believe that fishing is currently the primary activity in conflict with offshore wind deployment. This is followed by concerns about environmental protection. Tourism, on the other hand, received a comparatively lower number of votes as a conflicting activity.

Figure 9 MENTIMETER. Question 8

9. Which activity is most compatible with floating offshore wind?

The compatibility of various activities with Floating Offshore Wind (FOW) was assessed by participants, who rated each activity on a scale from 0 to 10. Leading the pack in compatibility was the utilization of an adaptive approach based on coordinated research, earning a robust rating of 7.9. Following closely behind was the establishment of collaboration agreements to leverage synergies between the two sectors, receiving a commendable rating of 7.3, indicative of strong compatibility. Employing the local population for operation and maintenance tasks garnered a notable rating of 7.4. Moderately compatible activities included allowing certain types of fishing within offshore wind farms under specific conditions, with a rating of 6.7, and permitting fishing vessels to transit through wind farm areas, earning a respectable rating of 6.2. Meanwhile, activities such as supporting fishing by designating migration corridors and aligning construction phases with fishing seasons received slightly

lower compatibility ratings of 5.9. In contrast, utilizing fish farms as tourist attractions was perceived as less compatible.

Figure 10 MENTIMETER. Question 9

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The Second Co-Creation Workshop delved not only into the barriers hindering the deployment of offshore wind energy in Spain but also heavily focused on determining the necessary measures to facilitate this deployment, taking into account the resources available in Galicia. As a culmination of the entire session, the following key milestones were clearly identified:

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Public Administration's Role and Dialogue Promotion: Lack of proactive dialogue promotion by public administrations, leading to frustration among participants over insufficient support for societal acceptance.</p> <p>Governmental Involvement and Support: Lack of governmental representation and effective decision-making in offshore wind farm projects, leading to frustration among stakeholders.</p>	<p>Encouragement for governments to initiate dialogue early on and facilitate transparent communication to foster societal acceptance and common ground.</p> <p>Recognition of the pivotal role of strong governance and commitment from all stakeholders, emphasizing the need for governmental involvement and support to overcome challenges and ensure project success.</p>
<p>Impact on fisheries: Lack of transparency and collaboration between the fishing and renewable energy sectors, hindering dialogue and data sharing.</p>	<p>Coexistence and collaboration: Emphasis on fostering equal conditions for coexistence and promoting positive intersectoral relations through dialogue facilitation and new integrated models.</p>
<p>Lack of trained professionals: Shortage of trained professionals to meet the demands of the emerging offshore wind energy sector</p>	<p>Enhanced training and educational programs: Implementing comprehensive training and educational initiatives, including dual training cycles, can address the shortage of skilled professionals. By investing in educational programs tailored to the needs of the offshore wind energy sector, regions can cultivate a capable workforce to support industry growth.</p> <p>Perception shift towards opportunity: Instead of viewing the shortage of trained professionals as a drawback, stakeholders should recognize it as an opportunity to foster regional growth within the sector. Promoting education and career opportunities in offshore wind energy can attract talent and stimulate economic development in the region.</p>

<p>Infrastructure Limitations and Cost Concerns: Absence of adequate space and port infrastructure for offshore wind deployments, compounded by high costs and infrastructure limitations.</p>	<p>Advocacy for investment in infrastructure development and cost-reduction strategies to address deployment challenges.</p>
<p>Dealing with onshore wind projects mistakes: Past shortcomings in the approval process for onshore wind farms and legal disputes leading to investment risks.</p>	<p>Cautionary approach to avoid repeating mistakes and promote transparency in project approvals to mitigate investment risks.</p>
<p>Best Practices and Benchmarking: Uncertainty and misinformation regarding best practices and benchmarks, hindering the implementation of optimal strategies.</p>	<p>Advocacy for clearer benchmarks and knowledge exchange with successful examples from other countries to inform decision-making and implementation.</p>